

Near-Infrared Light-Activated Antibacterial Efficiency of Flower-like MoS₂ with Varying Concentrations

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In this study, flower-like MoS₂ particles with a 2H crystal structure were synthesized via a hydrothermal method to evaluate their photothermal efficiency and antibacterial activity against Staphylococcus aureus and Escherichia coli. The structural, morphological, optical, and photothermal properties of the synthesized MoS₂ were comprehensively characterized. X-ray diffraction analysis confirmed that MoS₂ formed as 2H with no detectable impurities, while electron microscopy revealed a flower-like morphology. Optical characterization in the 400–1000 nm wavelength range indicated a direct band gap of approximately 1.9 eV. Photothermal performance was investigated using 808 nm laser irradiation in combination with thermal imaging, which demonstrated a maximum temperature increase of 46 °C at a concentration of 1000 µg mL⁻¹ and uniform heat distribution throughout the solution. Furthermore, antibacterial tests using agar plates showed that the antibacterial activity of MoS₂ was more pronounced at lower concentrations for both bacterial species, suggesting a concentration-dependent effect.

1. Introduction

As time progresses, bacterial infections are becoming increasingly severe, contributing to rising mortality rates worldwide [1]. Besides, the widespread and excessive use of antibiotic has led to the development of resistance in bacteria, complicating their eradication and creating significant public health challenges [1-3]. Recent advancements in nanotechnology have facilitated the development of novel antibacterial strategies and materials to fight bacterial infections effectively [1, 4-6]. It has been proven by many the studies that diverse stimulations like, light and magnetic field, materials show antibacterial effect and hinders effect of bacteria [1, 7, 8]. In particular, the light stimulation, especially near infrared (NIR) irritation is the best choice in different aspects [1, 9]. Materials interacting with NIR (700–1000 nm) light creating heat to eradicate pathogens or diseased cells, has emerged as a non-invasive and efficient treatment modality, particularly in biomedical applications [9-13].

Transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) have emerged as promising candidates for antibacterial applications due to their unique properties, including biocompatibility, tunable structural

parameters, cost-effectiveness, environmental friendliness, and favourable physicochemical characteristics [5, 14-16]. Among TMDs, molybdenum disulfide (MoS₂) emerges as a widely utilized material in diverse applications such as hydrogen evolution, photovoltaics, supercapacitors, microwave absorption, sensing, and drug delivery [17-23]. Within a single layer of MoS₂, molybdenum (Mo) and sulphur (S) atoms form covalent bonds, whereas weak van der Waals forces connect neighbouring layers [24, 25]. MoS₂ can crystallize in three distinct polymorphs: 2H (a thermodynamically stable semiconducting phase with hexagonal symmetry), 1T (a metastable semi metallic phase with trigonal symmetry), and 3R (semiconducting phase with rhombohedral symmetry) [26, 27]. The coordination of Mo and S atoms varies among these phases: both 2H and 3R exhibit trigonal prismatic coordination, while 1T adopts an octahedral configuration. This difference in coordination significantly influences the electronic structure of MoS₂, resulting in semiconducting behaviour in the 2H and 3R phases and semi metallic behaviour in the 1T phase [28]. Moreover, the bandgap of 2H MoS₂ is highly

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dependent on the number of layers. As the layer thickness decreases, the bandgap increases from approximately 1.2 eV to 1.9 eV, accompanied by a transition from indirect to direct bandgap characteristics [24, 29, 30]. In addition to its electronic and optical properties, MoS₂ demonstrates strong NIR absorption, low toxicity, and excellent photothermal conversion efficiency, making it a promising candidate for photothermal antibacterial applications [14, 31-35]. It has been shown that MoS₂ induces membrane stress and generates reactive oxygen species (ROS), further enhancing its contributing to its potential antibacterial properties [14].

Herein, flower-like MoS₂ particles were synthesized via hydrothermal synthesis, and their structural, morphological, optical, and photothermal properties were characterized. Additionally, the NIR-induced antibacterial activity of MoS₂ was evaluated against *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*) and *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*). The results indicate that MoS₂ crystallizes in the 2H phase and forms a flower-like morphology. Optical characterization confirmed a direct bandgap of 1.9 eV. Photothermal experiments revealed a maximum temperature of 46°C at a concentration of 1000 µg mL⁻¹, with thermal camera imaging indicating uniform heating in solution. Notably, higher antibacterial efficacy was achieved at lower MoS₂ concentrations.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Structural characteristics

Figure 1 illustrates the diffraction patterns of the synthesized samples. The black vertical lines at the bottom of the diffraction data correspond to the JCPDS card for trigonal prismatic (2H) MoS₂ with a space group P63/mmc (Hexagonal crystal system a: 3.1612 Å, b: 3.1612 Å and c: 12.2985 Å, JCPDS: 00-037-1492). It can be seen from the figure that the diffraction pattern of the synthesized samples aligns closely with reference card data. The primary peak of 2H MoS₂, associated with the (002) plane, appears at 2θ = 14.01°, consistent with literature values [38-40]. Additional peaks observed at 2θ = 32.73°, 36.32°, and 57.90° correspond to the (100), (102), and (110) planes, respectively. No impurities or secondary phases were detected in the diffraction data.

2.2. Morphological characteristics

The morphological characteristics of flower-like MoS₂ particles are shown in Fig. 2. The images reveal that MoS₂ forms flower-like structures, resulting from the assembly of nanosheets. This morphology emerges through a process involving

nucleation and growth of nanosheets, followed by their self-organization into a preferred orientation [41, 42]. The average particle size was determined using the X'Pert HighScore software, analysing 100 particles with a lognormal distribution fit. The calculations yielded an average particle size of 2.53 µm. Despite challenges in size determination due to particle agglomeration, measurements were performed by selecting particles as indicated by pink arrows in Fig. 2(a).

Figure 1. XRD pattern of synthesized samples.

2.3. Optical properties

The optical properties of the synthesized MoS₂ samples were examined using UV-Vis spectroscopy across the 400–1000 nm wavelength range, as shown in Fig. 3. The absorption spectra display a broad absorption band. Typically, MoS₂ exhibits characteristic peaks at ~350, 440, 600, and 650 nm [43-45]. In this study, however, these four characteristic peaks are absent, likely due to the excitonic properties of MoS₂ [44, 46]. Additionally, Tauc plots were generated using the following equation (Eq. 1),

$$(\alpha h\nu)^{1/n} = A(h\nu - E_g) \quad (1)$$

where α is the absorption coefficient, $h\nu$ represents the incident photon energy, A is energy independent constant, and n is an exponent determined by the type of electronic transition ($n = 1/2$ for direct transitions, $n = 2$ for indirect transitions). From the Tauc plots, the direct bandgap was calculated to be 1.9 eV, and the indirect bandgap was 1.4 eV, both of which align well with literature values [47, 48].

2.4. Photothermal properties

The photothermal characteristics of MoS₂ particles were first studied under 808 nm NIR irradiation at a power density of 2.5 W cm⁻², across concentrations of 50, 100, 250, 500, and 1000 µg mL⁻¹, as depicted in Fig. 4(a). Upon light exposure,

Figure 2. Morphological features of flower like MoS₂ particles, (a) SEM image and (b) Particle size distribution graph.

Figure 3. Optical properties of MoS₂, (a) absorbance spectrum and (b-c) Tauc plots.

all samples show a rapid temperature increase within the initial 0–100 seconds, after which the temperature increase rate diminishes. The figure also indicates that photothermal activity increases with increasing particle concentration, likely due to the greater number of active sites available for heat generation. The maximum temperature, recorded at 46°C, corresponds to the 1000 μg mL⁻¹ concentration. A thermal camera image or contour plot, in Fig. 4(b), confirms the temperature increase over the time period.

Subsequently, the sample exhibiting superior performance (1000 μg mL⁻¹) was further analyzed to explore the dependence of photothermal activity on power density. Fig. 4(c) illustrates the response at power density levels of 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, and 2.5 W cm⁻², confirming that maximum achievable temperature increases with higher power density, as expected. Furthermore, the photothermal cycling behaviour of MoS₂ particles was investigated through five consecutive on/off cycles of 808 nm NIR irradiation, as shown in Fig. 5(a). Each cycle exhibited almost consistent temperatures, demonstrating the excellent photothermal stability of the MoS₂ particles. The time constant (τ) and photothermal conversion efficiency were calculated using Eq. 4 and the data illustrated in Fig 5(b). The τ and photothermal conversion efficiency values were found as 317.2 s and 55.7%, respectively.

2.5. Antibacterial activity

Figure 6 illustrates the *in vitro* antibacterial activity of the synthesized sample against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* without NIR irradiation. As can be seen from the images that there is no reduction in bacterial presence without irradiation. However, when activated by light, an antibacterial effect was observed, as shown in Fig. 7. According to the images, the incubated bacterial concentration decreased under light activation. Furthermore, The antibacterial activity (%) of MoS₂ nanoparticles as a function of concentration against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* is presented in Figs. 7(b) and 7(d). For both bacterial cultures, antibacterial activity was strongly dependent on the concentration of MoS₂. As illustrated in graphs, lower concentrations of MoS₂ resulted in higher antibacterial activity, indicating that reduced concentrations are more effective in eliminating bacteria. It can be seen from the images (see Figs. 7(a) and (c)) that material exhibit enhanced antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* when concentration is decreased. This can be explained through the interplay of material properties and bacterial interactions. Generally, MoS₂ behaves as hydrophobic material and tend to aggregate in water environments [49, 50]. At higher concentrations it is believed that MoS₂ particles tend to aggregate in aqueous

Figure 4. Photothermal response of MoS₂, a) heating curve of MoS₂ at a power density of 2.5 W cm⁻², across concentrations of 50, 100, 250, 500, and 1000 µg mL⁻¹, b) thermal camera image of sample heating and c) heating curve of MoS₂ (1000 µg mL⁻¹) at power density levels of 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, and 2.5 W cm⁻²

Figure 5. (a) Photothermal stability of the particles under NIR light on/off cycles (NIR power density: 2.5 W cm⁻², MoS₂ concentration: 1000 µg mL⁻¹) and (b) linear regression curve obtained from cooling data in distilled water.

environments, forming clusters that reduce their effective surface area. Thus, this aggregation limits direct contact with bacterial cell walls, thereby decreasing the efficiency of antibacterial mechanisms such as membrane disruption with physical interaction or localized heating NIR irradiation [14]. Conversely, at lower concentrations, the nanoparticles remain well-dispersed, maximizing their surface area and enabling more effective interactions with bacterial cells.

3. Conclusion

In summary, flower-like MoS₂ particles with a 2H phase were successfully synthesized via a hydrothermal approach and demonstrated promising photothermal and antibacterial properties. The material exhibited strong NIR absorption with a direct band gap of 1.9 eV and achieved a significant temperature increase under 808 nm laser irradiation, indicating efficient

photothermal conversion. Moreover, MoS₂ displayed effective antibacterial activity against both *S. aureus* and *E. coli*, particularly at lower concentrations. These findings highlight the potential of MoS₂ as a biocompatible and efficient photothermal agent for antibacterial applications, paving the way for its further development in biomedical and antimicrobial technologies.

Method

Materials

Sodium molybdate dihydrate (Na₂MoO₄·2H₂O, Sigma-Aldrich, ≥99.0%), thiourea (CH₄N₂S, Alfa Aesar 99%), oxalic acid (C₂H₂O₄·2H₂O, ≥99.0%), Deionized (DI) water and ethyl alcohol (EA, Tekkim, 96%) were used for material synthesis and cleaning/washing purposes. Mueller-Hinton broth and Mueller-Hinton agar were purchased from Merck. Phosphate buffer saline (PBS) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich.

Figure 6. Spread agar plates belonging to (a) *S. aureus* and (b) *E. coli* bacteria without NIR irradiation (the number 1000, 500, 250, 100 and 50 refers to MoS₂ concentration as µg mL⁻¹).

Figure 7. Antibacterial activity of MoS₂ against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* bacteria with NIR irradiation, (a) Spread agar plates belonging to *S. aureus*, (b) Antibacterial activity of MoS₂ as a function of concentration against *S. aureus*, (c) Spread agar plates belonging to *E. coli* and (d) Antibacterial activity of MoS₂ as a function of concentration against *E. coli*.

Synthesis of flower-like MoS₂

Hydrothermal synthesis was employed to produce flower-like MoS₂ particles, with the process illustrated in Fig.8. To prepare the solution, Na₂MoO₄ was first dissolved in DI water and mixed with magnetic stirrer for 10 min. Next, thiourea was added and the solution left for mixing for another 10

min. Oxalic acid was subsequently introduced, followed by 1 h of mixing. The solution was then sealed in a Teflon-lined autoclave and heated at 200 °C for 20 h. The resulting black powders were washed several times with DI water and ethanol and dried at 80 °C in an oven under ambient conditions for 8 h.

Figure 8. Schematic illustration of the synthesis procedures of flower-like MoS₂.

Photothermal activity experiments

The photothermal properties of MoS₂ particles were investigated under 808 nm NIR light irradiation for 10 min, varying the NIR power density and particle concentration. Antibacterial efficiency was tested against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* using the spread plate technique under optimized conditions. MoS₂ suspensions at concentrations of 50, 100, 250, 500, and 1000 µg mL⁻¹ were sonicated in distilled water for 1 h. Then sonicated particles were transferred to quartz cuvettes for exposure to 808 nm NIR light at power densities levels of 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, and 2.5 W cm⁻² for 10 min. Real-time temperature changes in the suspensions were monitored using an Optris Xi 400 infrared camera, with corresponding thermal images captured. After 10 min of heating, the NIR source was turned off, and the cooling phase was recorded for an additional 10 min. In order to assess the photothermal stability of synthesized samples, temperature variation profiles were collected across five cycles. The photothermal conversion efficiency (η) was determined using Eq. 2,

$$\eta = \frac{h A \Delta t_{max} - Q_s}{I(1 - 10^{-A_\lambda})} \quad (2)$$

where h represents the heat transfer coefficient, A denotes the heated surface area of the cuvette, ΔT_{max} is the maximum temperature difference at steady state, Q_s refers the heat of the control solution, I indicates the NIR laser power, and A_λ is the absorbance of the materials at 808 nm [36]. The hA value was calculated using Eqs. 3-5, with the time constant τ derived from the $t - \ln\theta$ curve. Here, T_{amb}

and T_{max} represent the ambient and maximum temperatures, respectively, t is time, θ is a dimensionless parameter, and m and C_p denote the mass and heat capacity of the dispersion solution, respectively [37].

$$\theta = \frac{T - T_{amb}}{T_{max} - T_{amb}} \quad (3)$$

$$t = -\tau \ln\theta \quad (4)$$

$$hA = \frac{mC_p}{\tau} \quad (5)$$

Characterization techniques

The structural parameters of samples were specified using X-ray diffractometer with Cu-K α (Cu-K α = 1.5406 Å, range: 5-80° with a step size of 0.01°) radiation provided by the Rigaku-MiniFlex600. The morphological features and chemical state of elements in samples were specified by scanning electroscop (SEM, FEI-Quanta 650D FEG) equipped. The UV-vis-NIR spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-1800) in the wavelength range of 400-1000 nm was used to investigate optical properties of synthesized materials. Real-time temperature changes in the suspensions were monitored using an Optris Xi 400 infrared camera.

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Authors' contributions:

AA: Performed photothermal experiments/data collection, data analysis, and interpretation, drafted the paper. **AM:** Performed antibacterial experiments/data collection, data analysis, and interpretation, drafted the paper. **BK:** Synthesized materials, performed experiments/data collection, data analysis, and interpretation, drafted the paper, and provided grammatical revisions to the manuscript, provided revisions to scientific content of the manuscript

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Declaration of Ethical Standards

The author(s) of this article declare that the materials and methods used in this study do not require ethical committee permission and/or legal-special permission.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author used Grok 3 to correct the grammatical faults in the manuscript. After using this tool/service, the author reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest in this study.

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